

MATERIAL SYSTEMS DESIGN FOR LONG-TERM PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The fundamental concept behind the use of composite material systems is the ability to combine materials in a specific way to achieve specific properties and performance, based on the combined action and interaction of the constituents and related interface/interphases. There is a significant body of literature which deals with the manner in which such combinations can be made to produce certain properties such as stiffness (effective stiffness concepts). There is a considerably smaller body of literature which addresses the question of how to combine materials in composite systems to achieve specific strength level and to design material systems for long-term performance; e.g., for reliability, durability, and damage tolerance.

The present paper deals with this latter topic in some detail. Material parameters which control long-term behavior under cyclic and sustained mechanical, thermal, and chemical loading will be identified. Micromechanical representations will be used as a basis for the interpretation and design variables of the effect of synthesis, processing, and manufacturing on the long-term performance. Relationships which combine those parameters in such a way as to control the long-term properties and performance of materials will be established. Analytical approaches to the solution of those relationships will be discussed. Special attention will be given to the tensile-controlled behavior and creep-fatigue interaction. Results of both theoretical predictions and experimental tests will be presented.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Material Systems; Design; Long-term Performance.

STRENGTH IS A PROCESS

We will focus our attention on the strength of material systems (and the remaining strength under long-term conditions) as a measure of performance, and begin with the claim that strength is a process which is greatly influenced by long-term conditions such as mechanical loading, thermal changes, and chemical environments.

In deference to typical current engineering practice, we will consider continuous fiber-reinforced composite material systems which may be laminated, and which may have micro-constituents including fibers, matrix material, interfaces, and interphase regions which are organic or inorganic molecules and compounds. Such materials are typified by two characteristics which are of considerable importance to the present discussion.

1. Inhomogeneous Discontinuities between phases at the micro level are a source of sharp gradients (and possibly discontinuities) in material behavior, which may act as a nucleations mechanism for damage development and an obstruction to damage growth.

2. Anisotropic The arrangement of micro-constituents (including fibers, matrix, interfaces, and interphases) gives rise to anisotropic material response at the global level which creates a general tendency for multi-dimensional complex stress states; coupling of extensional, shear, and bending deformational behavior; complexity of damage and failure modes; and complex stress redistribution during damage development.

As a consequence of these factors, the failure of a material system element is normally a result of the nucleation of many micro-defects, possibly in a widely distributed fashion, which may grow and are likely to interact in such a way to alter the material state and stress state at the local level such that the remaining strength of the material is exceeded and failure ensues, i.e., failure is a process. This is true for quasi-static loading, and it is especially true for long-term loading, the subject of our current discussion. Figure 1 shows the physical consequence of these facts. Even under short term conditions, the failure of a fibrous reinforced composite is complex as shown in Fig. 1a. However, under long-term loading conditions (at $R=0.1$ and 60% of the ultimate strength in this instance) the failure mode is remarkably complex as shown in Fig. 1b. Indeed, under long-term conditions, the failure process involves a complex damage development, a process which is well documented in the literature for many composite material systems (Refs. 1 and 2).

Since failure is a process in material systems, it is not possible to properly model the failure of such a system or predict the remaining strength and life of such a system by considering only the initial material state and stress state, nor is it possible to establish correct models or predictions by the use of "progressive damage concepts" which do not properly account for all material state or stress state changes. A method of solution of such problems has been suggested by Reifsnider, et al. (Refs. 3 and 4).

Figure 2 illustrates the critical element concept. It is assumed that the damage associated with property and performance degradation is widely and uniformly distributed. It is further assumed that, for a specific failure mode, a "representative volume" of material can be chosen from that uniform distribution such that the state of material and state of stress in that volume are typical of all other such volumes in the material, and that those details are sufficient to describe the final failure event.

It is further postulated that this representative volume can be divided into "critical elements" which remain intact (and contiguous in the continuum sense) until the final failure event, i.e., the failure of these critical elements defines the failure of the representative volume and the failure of the component. Moreover, it is further assumed that the remaining material in the representative volume consists of "subcritical elements" in the sense that their failure (such as cracking, rupture, or other irreversible behavior) does not cause failure of the representative volume or of the component. As Fig. 2 suggests, the critical elements are defined by failure modes which are carefully established by laboratory investigations, and usually involve a failure process consisting of a variety of damage modes as discussed above. For many of the composite material systems in current use, matrix constituent materials are typical contributors to subcritical damage, and fiber failure is frequently involved in the final failure process and, therefore, are usually part of the critical element for a given failure mode.

We will adopt the critical element concept as a vehicle for our discussion of the failure process. Indeed, we will address this process as the mechanism which alters the material state and stress state in the representative volume in such a way that

strength is reduced during the long-term behavior of a material system used in an engineering component subjected to various in-service environments. Figure 3 illustrates the nature of these changes schematically. Reading from the top of that figure, the remaining strength of the critical element which controls failure for a given loading condition and material system can be discussed in terms of changing properties such as a reduction in stiffness, as well as the changes in local stress state as suggested by the "local failure function" illustrated in Fig. 3. The lower most curve suggests the rate of damage development over the life of the engineering component. While each of these curves is presented in schematic form, their shape is typical of observations obtained from fiber-reinforced laminated composite material systems (Refs. 1 and 2). If we are to design material systems for long-term performance, we must understand the long-term processes which reduce properties of these systems at the local level, i.e., in the representative volumes and critical and subcritical elements which control failure modes that determine the remaining strength and life of the engineering components made from such systems. Hence, as suggested in Fig. 3, we must understand the details of the primary nucleation events, the growth, development, and localization events, and the coupling and secondary nucleation events which contribute to and control the final failure event. Of course, a complete understanding of all of these events is not presently at hand. However, this mechanistic approach (or an equivalent mechanistic approach) must be taken if serious thought is given to the rigorous design of material systems. Simply stated, it is not possible to understand how to put material systems together unless we fully understand how they come apart.

MICROMECHANICAL STRENGTH MODELS ARE THE KEY TO MATERIAL SYSTEM DESIGN

The parameters which must be controlled and combined to design material systems can be properly identified from the development of micromechanical strength models which correctly represent the failure process in representative volumes for the specific failure modes that control long-term performance.

Due to a severe limitation of space in this presentation, we will discuss only two short examples of this approach. The first example is a representation of the fiber-controlled failure under tension of fiber-reinforced composite systems.

For continuous fiber-reinforced composite materials, two primary considerations dominate the failure processes which control tensile strength. One of them is bundle strength, i.e., the capacity of a bundle of fibers to hold a tensile load when each fiber can break only once and the load is redistributed to the rest of the fibers evenly each time one fiber breaks. The second factor is the stress concentration which one fiber break causes in adjacent fibers. The micromechanical strength formulas which consider such an effect on tensile strength are typified by the relationships suggested by Batdorf (Ref. 5).

$$Q_{i+1} = Q_i n_i \lambda_i \left[\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right]^m, \quad Q_1 = NL \left[\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right], \quad \lambda_i = 2\delta_i \frac{C_i^{m+1} - 1}{(C_i - 1)(m+1)} \quad (1)$$

for a composite with N fibers of length L , each having n_i nearest neighbors. λ_i is a parameter proportional to the stress concentration, C , and the ineffective length, δ . σ_0 is proportional to the average strength of the fibers.

Bundle strength and local stress concentration effects can be combined in the following fashion. The shear and normal stresses, obtained in the classic shear lag analysis, are written as (Ref. 6).

$$\tau_m(x) = \frac{-r_f \eta \sigma_a E_f}{2E_c} \exp(-\eta x) \quad (2)$$

and

$$\sigma_f(x) = \frac{\sigma_a E_f}{E_c} [1 - \exp(-\eta x)] \quad (3)$$

where

$$\eta^2 = \left\{ \frac{2G_m}{E_f(r_m - r_f)r_f} \right\} \left\{ 1 + \frac{E_f}{E_c} \left[\frac{r_f^2}{r_c^2 - r_m^2} \right] \right\}, \quad (4)$$

E is Young's modulus and G is the shear modulus. The subscripts f, m, and c denote quantities associated with the fiber, matrix, and composite, respectively. The constant r defines a radius from the center of the broken fiber, and σ_a is the constant applied stress.

In the shear lag analysis, only the broken fiber is considered, and the rest of the composite is treated as a homogeneous material with uniform displacement $u_c(x)$. However, in terms of fiber fracture, the neighboring fibers are over-stressed and may be caused to fail.

The shear stress in the matrix $\tau_m(x)$ of the shear lag analysis (Eqn. (2)) can be modified to include the effect of stress concentration. We propose that

$$\tau_m(x) = \frac{-r_f \eta \sigma_a E_f}{2E_c} \exp(-\eta x) f(x) \quad (5)$$

where $f(x)$ is an influence function with regard to stress concentration effects. As a first approximation, we choose $f(x) = Ax + B$, in which A and B are constants. The analysis derived herein, while case specific, can be modified to consider other forms of damage and interface effects.

The constants A and B, as well as shear and tensile stresses, can be determined from local stress analysis (Ref. 7). The ratio of the fiber stress at $x=\delta$ to the far-field fiber stress is then related to the efficiency parameter ϕ

$$\phi = \frac{\sigma_f(\delta)}{\sigma_f(\infty)}, \quad (6)$$

which yields

$$\phi = \left[C + \frac{(1-C)}{\delta\eta} \right] [1 - \exp(-\eta\delta)] - \frac{(1-C)}{\delta\eta} [(\eta\delta + 1)\exp(-\eta\delta) - 1]. \quad (7)$$

From the above equation we know that C increases as δ decreases, which suggests that when the ineffective length becomes smaller, the resulting stress concentration in the unbroken fiber becomes larger. This makes physical sense, that is, as the stress concentration effects are confined to a smaller region (i.e., δ decreases) the value of the stress concentration for a particular x must increase to maintain

equilibrium.

Combining Eqn. 7 with the micromechanics analyses of Refs. 8 or 9, we can solve for both the stress concentration factor C_1 , and for the ineffective length δ_1 , for any given composite material. Hence, the plot $\text{Ln}(\sigma)$ vs. $\text{Ln}(Q_1)$ constructed from Eqn. (1) forms a failure envelope which defines the composite strength, as discussed by Batdorf (Ref. 5). If the stress σ_1 is defined as the stress value at the intersection of Q_1 and the horizontal line $Q_1=1$, we look for the first σ_1 such that $\sigma_1 > \sigma_{i+1}$. That σ_1 represents the ultimate composite stress (Ref. 7).

Figure 4 illustrates predicted tensile strength for a typical graphite-reinforced polymeric matrix system in which the relative stiffness of the fibers and matrix are varied. The variation in strength is shown for two values of the Weibull shape factor of the statistical distribution of fiber strength in that system. The micromechanical strength analysis predicts that there are two primary regions of strength. The region to the left of Fig. 4 is dominated by stress concentration effects which decrease the strength as the stiffness of the matrix increases in comparison to that of the fiber and creates a more rapid buildup of stress in the broken fiber and a corresponding more intense stress concentration in the neighboring fibers. To the right of the diagram in Fig. 4, the strength is dominated by fiber bundle effects wherein the ineffective length increases as the relative stiffness of the matrix decreases so that fiber failures create a local stress field which spreads over increasing distances to interact with other fiber failures and cause a decrease in composite strength. The micromechanical strength analysis predicts an optimum choice of this (and other) material property ratio, an important departure from previous treatments of this problem. It is well established that ceramic composite systems are dominated by stress concentration effects on the left of the diagram in Fig. 4 while polymeric composite systems tend to be dominated by bundle strength and ineffective length factors as depicted on the right of that diagram.

Figure 5 identifies additional design parameters by showing the variation of the local stress concentration as a function of fiber and matrix stiffness and the volume fraction of fibers in the system. In addition, it can be seen that the stress concentration factor is greatly influenced by the number of broken fibers, leading to the conclusion that only a relatively small number of fibers will break before the component breaks, a result which defines the necessary size of our representative volume when boundary value problems are solved for local stress states.

The second example that we will use to define design parameters is for compression failure of a fiber-reinforced composite system. For this discussion we will use a representation from the literature for compressive strength in which the shear strength of a fiber-reinforced lamina, τ_c , the in-plane shear stiffness of the lamina, G_{Lt} , the volume fraction of the fibers, z_f , the Young's modulus of the fibers, E_f , the radius of the fibers, r , and the initial displacement of the fibers from the direction of axial loading, f_0 , which occurs over a microbuckling length, ℓ , combined to determine the strength in compression, σ_c , according to the relationship

$$\sigma_c = \frac{G_{Lt} + \frac{\pi^2}{4} \nu_f E_f \left[\frac{r}{\ell} \right]^2}{1 + \left[\frac{\pi f_0}{\ell} \right] \frac{G_{Lt}}{\tau_c}} \quad (8)$$

where the in-plane shear stiffness is given by

$$G_{Lt} = \frac{E_f \nu_f}{2} \left[\frac{h}{l} \right]^2 \left[1 + \left[\frac{h}{l} \right]^2 \frac{E_f l}{G_f 4} \right] \quad (9)$$

in which h is the fiber diameter. These relationships describe the failure process in a representative volume whose dimensions are defined by a microbuckling failure mode as represented in Fig. 2.

For these two abbreviated examples, Eqns. 1-9 define a variety of parameters which may change during the lifetime of an engineering component constructed from a composite material system. However, the changes in properties of such a component can be expressed in terms of the changes in these parameters, i.e., the global properties of strength and stiffness can be expressed in terms of the micromechanical parameters that appear in Eqns. 1-9. Hence, these parameters and their changes can be used to design material systems for long-term performance.

MATERIAL SYSTEM DESIGN FOR PERFORMANCE

Micromechanical strength representations of failure processes under long-term loading conditions can be used in combination with critical element concepts to design material systems for long-term performance by demonstrating sensitivity to changes in material parameters.

In the foregoing paragraphs we have discussed how material parameters such as constituent stiffnesses and strengths, interface stiffnesses and strengths, geometric factors including dimensions and arrangements, and statistical factors such as Weibull location and shape parameters enter the micromechanical strength relationships which control composite strength for fiber-dominated tension and compression failure modes. Comparable formulas could have been displayed for effective stiffness of such materials (as widely discussed in the literature). These micromechanical strength and stiffness relationships can be used to discuss the remaining strength and stiffness of the critical element in a representative volume for a specific failure mode under long-term conditions in terms of the micromechanical "design parameters" just mentioned. This provides a time-dependent definition of "material state" in the critical element, and therefore in the representative volume, and in the composite system. The local stress state in which the critical element operates is defined by the proper boundary value problems for the failure modes associated with the material states discussed. When these material states and stress states are compared with an appropriate philosophy of failure, the remaining strength and life of the composite system can be predicted, as we have described in the literature (Refs. 3, 4, 11 and 12). Hence, it is possible to determine if changes in such micro-parameters has matrix yield strength, ineffective length (do to such things as splitting along fibers or plasticity of the matrix or chemical action at the interface between fiber and matrix), or matrix compliance (possibly due to viscoelastic creep) cause significant or insignificant changes in the long-term remaining strength and life of material systems, and to use that information to design such systems for preferred performance characteristics under long-term conditions. Such studies and corresponding design efforts are under way in our laboratories using this approach.

CLOSURE

A systematic philosophy for the design of material systems for long-term performance has been presented. The philosophy is based on the representation of strength and stiffness of such systems in terms of the micro-parameters associated with constituent properties, arrangements, and interfaces and interphases between those constituents. The application of this approach is, however, only in the beginning stages. Nevertheless, even the brief description presented above and our current experience suggest several surprising results. Examination of Eqns. 1-9, and their sensitivity to various parameters which appear in those equations,

suggests that, although fibers control the tension and compression strength in the failure modes described by those equations, the greatest sensitivity to change in strength enters through changes in matrix properties under long-term mechanical, thermal, and chemical conditions. There are several exceptions to this generality, especially when such things as the stiffness of the fiber is altered by phenomena such as chemical attack or morphological alterations in which case the resulting tension and compression strength is greatly affected. However, in most cases, such things as matrix compliance changes and interface changes including interface yielding and fiber matrix splitting play a surprisingly large role in the variation of composite strength. Another somewhat surprising factor is the influence of the shape factor which describes the spread in the statistical strength of the reinforcing fibers. That shape factor plays a substantial role in the failure process under quasi-static conditions, and influences the choice of relative stiffnesses of the matrix and fiber materials to attain an optimum initial strength for the material system. Finally, it should be emphasized that changes in material state associated with the micromechanical equations developed above, and other companion equations required for other failure processes, are not sufficient descriptions of the sensitivity of a material system to changing long-term conditions. It is also essential to solve the proper local boundary value problem for a given failure mode to establish the state of stress which can be compared to the evolving change in the state of the material described by those or other equations. Figure 6 illustrates this point for the fully-reversed cyclic fatigue loading of a notched composite laminate in which the damage development causes such large local stress redistributions that strength of the component increases dramatically in tension while decreasing monotonically in compression. The predictions shown in that figure were made with the MRLife code developed in our laboratory which considers not only changes in the material state but also changes in the local stress state in the critical element associated with subcritical damage.

While this general enterprise of designing material systems is certainly in its infancy, a solid foundation and a systematic approach is available for such a pursuit. Moreover, the potential savings in time and expense associated with trial and error methods of making and testing material systems, and the potential gains in performance that are available from such a systematic approach argue strongly for a more dedicated effort to more fully develop the details of this philosophy.

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Figure 1. Specimen failure modes for short term (a) and long term (b) cyclic loading of unidirectional graphite epoxy coupons.

Figure 2. Flow diagram of the "critical element concept" and examples of failure modes which control the model.

Figure 3. Performance characteristics associated with material system design.

Figure 4. Strength as a function of material properties and Weibull shape parameter for bundle theory alone (solid line) and from the current model (dotted lines).

Figure 5. Stress concentration in nearest neighbor fibers as a function of E_f/G_m (dashed lines) and volume fraction of fibers (solid lines) for 1-4 broken fibers.

Figure 6. Comparison of predicted and observed remaining strength of center-notched graphite epoxy laminate coupons subjected to full-reversed cyclic loading. Predictions made with MRLife code.